

Studies on Spiroheterocyclic Nitrogen Compounds. Part I : Synthesis of Some New Spiro Pyrazolines, Isoxazolines and Pyrimidinethiones Containing Benzanilide Moiety

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Reaction of isatin with 4-acetylbenzanilide derivatives gave 3-hydroxy-3-(phenacyl-*para*-substituted benzoylamino) oxindoles (2). Dehydration of (2) gave 3-(phenacylidene-*para*-substituted benzoylamino)-2-indolinones (3). Cyclocondensation of (3) with hydrazinehydrate, phenylhydrazine, phenylthiourea and hydroxylamine afforded new spiro pyrazolines (4, 5), pyrimidinethiones (6) and isoxazolines (7) containing benzanilide moiety. The structures of the final products were confirmed by spectral and micro-analytical data.

IN view of the germicidal properties of the substituted benzanilides which have been studied widely¹⁻³, coupled with the importance of spiro pyrazolines, isoxazolines and pyrimidinethiones in different biological and industrial aspects have led us to synthesize such new combined molecules⁴.

The reaction of isatin with substituted benzanilides (1) was carried out in the presence of piperidine as a basic catalyst giving rise to 3-hydroxy-3-(phenacyl-*para*-substituted benzoylamino) oxindoles (2) in quantitative yields. The structure of (2) was established from microanalytical data as well as the ir spectra which showed a well defined band in the regions 3520 (OH) and 1720 cm⁻¹ (cyclic imide).

Dehydration of (2) by dilute alcoholic hydrochloric acid or by hydrochloric acid in the presence of acetic acid gave 3-(phenacylidene-*para*-substituted benzoylamino)-2-indolinones (3) in good yields (Scheme 1). Ir spectra of (3) showed a characteristic band at 1725-1703 cm⁻¹ (α,β -unsaturated ketone).

Cyclocondensation of α,β -unsaturated ketone with hydrazines have been intensively investigated by many workers^{5,6}, which in most cases gave pyrazolines. Accordingly, the reaction^{7,8} of (3) with hydrazine, phenylhydrazine, phenylthiourea and/or hydroxylamine gave the corresponding new spiro pyrazolines (4, 5), spiro pyrimidinethiones (6) and spiroisoxazolines (7) derivatives (Scheme 1). Acetic acid was recommended in the reaction of (3) with hydrazine which gave spiro N-acetylpyrazolines (4), while piperidine was used as a catalyst in the reaction of phenylhydrazine giving spiro N-phenylpyrazolines (5). The ir spectra of these compounds showed bands at 1230 cm⁻¹ (C-N), and 1600 cm⁻¹ (C=N). The disappearance of band at 1690 cm⁻¹ (conjugated carbonyl) indicated the disruption of this group. On the other hand,

Scheme 1

interaction of (3) with phenylthiourea in the presence of alcoholic KOH⁹ afforded pyrimidinethiones (6); ν_{max} 1650-1600 (C-N), 1270 (C=S), 1460 (C-N=S) and 1720 cm⁻¹ (cyclic imide)¹⁰. The reaction between (3) and hydroxylamine hydrochloride in presence of alcoholic KOH¹¹ gave isoxazolines (7). Ir spectra of these compounds showed bands at 1660-1600 (C=N) and 1730-1700 cm⁻¹ (cyclic imide).

Experimental

M.p.s were uncorrected. The ir spectra were recorded on a Pye Unicam SP 200G spectrophotometer, using KBr discs.

Substituted benzanilides (1) : These were prepared according to procedures reported in the literature^{1,2}.

3-Hydroxy-3-(phenacyl-para-substituted benzoylamino) oxindoles (2) : A mixture of isatin and substituted benzanilides (1), (0.01 mol each) was dissolved in 100 ml absolute ethanol and diethylamine (10 drops) or piperidine was added. The mixture was allowed to stand overnight at room temperature. The yellow needles formed were recrystallised from ethanol. The results are listed in Table 1.

Compound	M.p. °C	Yield %	Molecular formula	Analysis % ; Found/(Calcd.)* N
2a	218	65	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₄	7.31 (7.25)
2b	225	76	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₄ Cl	6.53 (6.66)
2c	219	72	C ₂₃ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₄	9.90 (9.74)
2d	228	61	C ₂₄ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₄	6.75 (6.89)

* All compounds gave satisfactory C, H analyses.

3-(Phenacylidene-para-substituted benzoylamino)-2-indolinones (3) : (Method A) A mixture containing 5 g (2), 25 ml alcohol and 50 ml conc. hydrochloric acid was allowed to stand overnight (or was heated 100°, 1.5 h). Fine orange needles formed. (Method B) When a mixture containing 2 g (2), 0.5 ml conc. hydrochloric acid and 20 ml glacial acetic acid was warmed on the steam-bath (15 min), cooled, the same product formed as in method A. The results are listed in Table 2.

Compound	M.p. °C	Yield %	Molecular formula	Analysis % ; Found/(Calcd.)* N
3a	302	85	C ₂₃ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₃	7.52 (7.60)
3b	266	87	C ₂₃ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₃ Cl	7.01 (6.95)
3c	318	80	C ₂₃ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₃	10.29 (10.16)
3d	284	79	C ₂₄ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₃	7.12 (7.03)

* All compounds gave satisfactory C, H analyses.

Pyrazolines (4) and (5) : A mixture of (3) (0.01 mol) and hydrazinehydrate (50%) or phenylhydrazine (0.01 mol) in 50 ml ethanol was refluxed (3 h). In case of hydrazine hydrate 10 ml acetic

acid were added, however, piperidine was used as a catalyst. After concentration the precipitate formed was filtered off, washed with cold ethanol and recrystallised from acetic acid. The results are listed in Table 3.

Compound	M.p. °C	Yield %	Molecular formula	Analysis % ; Found/(Calcd.)* N
4a	350	52	C ₂₈ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₂	13.32 (13.20)
4b	144	55	C ₂₈ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₂ Cl	12.25 (12.21)
4c	350	49	C ₂₉ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₂	14.89 (14.92)
4d	148	45	C ₂₈ H ₂₂ N ₄ O ₂	12.30 (12.83)
5a	232	63	C ₂₉ H ₂₂ N ₄ O ₂	12.21 (12.22)
5b	135	57	C ₂₉ H ₂₂ N ₄ O ₂ Cl	11.40 (11.37)
5c	298	43	C ₂₉ H ₂₁ N ₄ O ₂	13.89 (13.91)
5d	188	49	C ₃₀ H ₂₄ N ₄ O ₂	11.51 (11.47)

* All compounds gave satisfactory C, H analyses.

Pyrimidinethiones (6) : A mixture of (3) (0.02 mol), phenylthiourea (0.02 mol), KOH (2 g), ethyl alcohol (100 ml) and water (2 ml) was refluxed (3 h). The heavy precipitate formed on concentration and cooling was filtered, dried and recrystallised from ethanol. The results are listed in Table 4.

Compound	M.p. °C	Yield %	Molecular formula	Analysis % ; Found/(Calcd.)* N
6a	165	55	C ₃₀ H ₂₂ N ₄ O ₂ S	11.25 (11.15)
6b	162	50	C ₃₀ H ₂₁ N ₄ O ₂ SOCl	10.39 (10.43)
6c	160	66	C ₃₀ H ₂₁ N ₄ O ₂ S	12.81 (12.79)
6d	228	63	C ₃₁ H ₂₄ N ₄ O ₂ S	10.62 (10.52)

* All compounds gave satisfactory C, H analyses.

Compound	M.p. °C	Yield %	Molecular formula	Analysis % ; Found/(Calcd.)* N
7a	190	39	C ₂₈ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₂	10.87 (10.96)
7b	156	35	C ₂₈ H ₁₆ N ₃ O ₂ Cl	10.12 (10.05)
7c	192	40	C ₂₈ H ₁₈ N ₃ O ₂	13.11 (13.08)
7d	222	46	C ₂₈ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₂	10.21 (10.16)

* All compounds gave satisfactory C, H analyses.

Isoxazolines (7): A mixture of (3) (0.02 mol), hydroxylamine hydrochloride (0.02 mol), potassium hydroxide (2 g), ethyl alcohol (100 ml) and water (2 ml) was refluxed (3 h). The heavy precipitate formed on concentration and cooling was filtered, dried and recrystallized from dioxane. The results are listed in Table 5.

References

1. D. P. ROMAN and R. C. MANRING in "Developments in Industrial Microbiology", ed., C. F. KODA, American Institute of Biological Sciences, Washington, D. C., 1967, Vol. 8, Chapter 3.
2. A. KRAUSHAAR, *Arsneim, Forsch.*, 1964, 4, 548.
3. N. J. LENNON, T. E. FURIA and H. W. ZUSSMAN, *Soap Chem. Specialities*, 1960, 36, No. 3, 51 ; No. 4, 56 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1960, 54, 13695).
4. M. A. EL-MAGHRABY and M. A. ABBADY, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1978, 16, 57.
5. L. I. SMITH and L. L. HOWARD, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 65, 159.
6. R. V. VON AVWERS and E. CAUER, *Ann.*, 1929, 470, 284.
7. H. G. LINDWALL and J. S. MCLENNAN, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 54, 4739.
8. Z. H. KHALIL, *Z. Naturforsch., Teil B*, 1978, 33, 105.
9. A. SAMMOUR, M. I. B. SELIM, M. M. NOUR and M. ABD-EL-HALIM, *U. A. R. J. Chem.*, 1970, 13, 7.
10. L. J. BELLAMY, "The Infrared Spectra of Complex Molecules", 2nd ed., Methuen and Co. Ltd., London, 1958.
11. M. A. ABBADY, A. A. KHALAF, A. E. ABDEL-RAHMAN and B. E. BAYOUMY, in the press.
12. B. E. BAYOUMY, Ph. D. Thesis, Assuit University, Egypt, 1982.